

Stability Constants of Complexes of 7-(α -*m*-nitro Anilino benzyl)-8-Quinolinol with Cu(II), Ni(II), VO(II) and Zn(II)

K. J. SHAH* and K. K. PATEL

University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Bhavnagar

Manuscript received 5 January 1977, revised 1 February 1978, accepted 14 March 1978

The paper deals with the determination of stability constants by potentiometric method of Cu(II), Ni(II), VO(II) and Zn(II) of the ligand *m*-NO₂-ABQ.

The stability constants were computed by several methods such as half integral, least squares, Linear plots, Hearon and Gilbert's and Olerup's method. They obey the Irving Williams rule. To check the validity of the results standard deviation σ was calculated.

In continuation of our work^{1,2} on 7-(α -Anilino benzyl)-8-quinolinol derivatives, the compound *m*-NO₂ (ABQ) was synthesized. The compound is prepared following the method of Phillips³. It is found to form complexes with Cu(II), Ni(II), VO(II) and Zn(II). They all form 1 : 2 complexes with this ligand.

The acid dissociation constant of the ligand was determined by half integral method and by pointwise calculation method. The stability constants are evaluated by different methods such as, half integral, least squares, linear plots Hearon and Gilberts and Olerups method. The value of standard deviation was calculated.

Experimental

It was synthesised by condensing 0.1M amine, 0.1M *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde and 0.1M 8-quinolinol in absolute alcohol to get compound(I) following the method of Phillips. It is crystallized from ethanol-acetone mixture as yellow crystals with m.p. 146°. The nitrogen and oxygen atoms of 8-quinolinol are donar atoms.

Metal solutions were prepared by dissolving metal nitrates B. D. H. AnalaR grade except vanadium for which VOSO₄ (B. D. H. England) was used and there solutions were prepared in double glass distilled water. The ligand solution was prepared in purified dioxane⁴. Nitric acid solution and KNO₃ solution were prepared in double distilled water.

Procedure

With a Phillips pH meter, and standard glass and Calomel electrodes pH values were measured. For pH measurements following solutions were prepared.

(a) *Metal titration* : 1 ml of 0.01M HNO₃ + 5ml of 1M KNO₃ + 5 ml 0.01M reagent solution in

dioxane + 7 ml of water + 30 ml of pure dioxane to maintain the dioxane : water volume ratio of 70 : 30.

(b) *Reagent titration* : Same as above except that the metal salt solution was replaced by equivalent amount of pure distilled water.

(c) *Acid titration* : Same as above described under metal titration except that the metal salt solution and reagent solutions were replaced by equivalent amount of distilled and pure dioxane.

These solutions were titrated against standard alkali NaOH. The titration curves, i.e., pH versus volume of alkali added were plotted.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves the average number of protons, \bar{n}_H may be calculated as usual⁵.

The formation curves of the proton-ligand complexes were plotted by plotting \bar{n}_H against B (pH meter readings).

From these formation curves the P_{K^H} is directly obtained. This is also obtained⁶ by plotting

$\log \frac{\bar{n}_H}{1-\bar{n}_H}$ against B to obtain a best straight line.

Thus the value is also obtained by pointwise calculations, the average value obtained by these two methods is 9.90.

The metal-ligand stability constants were also obtained by calculating \bar{n} and pL using Irving-Rossotti method⁵.

The metal-ligand stability constants can be directly read by plotting formation curves, i.e., \bar{n} versus pL . They are also obtained by Least squares method⁶, method of Linear plots⁷ and Olerups method⁸.

* For correspondence.

The results obtained by different methods are given in Table 1.

TABLE—1							
t=25±1°	0.1M KNO ₃				70% dioxane		
Method	I	II	III	IV	Mean	σ Standard deviation	
Metal							×
Cu(II)	10.42	9.54	10.16	9.90	9.95	log k_1	0.051
	9.90	10.55	10.02	11.24	10.42	log k_2	
	20.22	20.13	20.18	21.14	20.35	log β_2	
VO(II)	9.94	9.05	10.08	9.48	9.84	log k_1	0.095
	9.43	10.44	9.39	9.82	9.68	log k_2	
	19.37	19.49	19.47	19.30	19.39	log β_2	
Ni(II)	8.90	8.05	8.17	9.18	8.76	log k_1	0.074
	8.02	9.44	8.96	8.17	8.61	log k_2	
	17.36	17.49	17.13	17.35	17.34	log $k\beta_2$	
Zn(II)	8.53	7.64	8.92	8.68	8.63	log k_1	0.054
	7.87	9.04	7.34	7.25	7.65	log k_2	
	16.40	16.68	16.76	15.93	16.34	log β_2	

(I) Half integral, (II) Linear plots, (III) Least squares, (IV) Olerup's.

The order of stability for $\log k_1$ indicates
VO(II) < Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II)

The order of stability follows Irving-Williams rule⁸. To check the validity of the results \bar{n} was recalculated using Least squares method's $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$. The $\Delta\bar{n}$ thus obtained was used to

calculate standard deviation σ^7 using the relation

$$\sigma = \pm \left[\frac{(\sum \Delta \bar{n})^2}{N} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

The value of σ is given in Table 1. The values of σ are small, i.e., the limits of errors are small in each case.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. K. A. Thaker, Prof. & Head, University Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University for giving research facilities.

References

1. Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH and R. S. PATEL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1975, **13**, 847-8.
2. Y. N. BHATT, K. K. PATEL, K. J. SHAH and R. S. PATEL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 218.
3. J. P. PHILLIPS, R. KROWN and Q. FERNANDO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **74**, 4306.
4. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans, 1961, p. 177.
5. H. M. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
6. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERGENT, "Ionisation Constants of Acids and Bases", John Wiley and Sons, New York, p. 164.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397.
8. H. OLERUP, *Järnkloridernas Komplexitete (diss.)*, Lunds-Lunds Universitets—Rokhandel, Lund, 1944.
9. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAMS, *Nature*, 1948, **62**, 746.